

Studies on Triortho-periodato Tetracobaltic(III) Acid. Part—II

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The compound $H_2[Co_4I_2O_{24}H_{12}].6H_2O$ has been prepared following two known methods—one is an alkaline method and the other is an acid method. TGA, IR and electronic spectra and powder X-ray studies have been made to throw light on its structure.

IN one of our previous communications¹, we discussed some of the properties of the interesting compound, triortho-periodatotetracobaltic(III) acid. We have now carried out thermal, spectral and powder X-ray studies of this compound. The compound has further been prepared following two known methods, the alkaline² and the acid methods³. The composition of the compound has been formulated as $H_2[Co_4I_2O_{24}H_{12}].6H_2O$. Analyses have confirmed that the composition is independent of the method of preparation. Powder X-ray study has confirmed the similarity of the crystalline nature of the compound prepared by either of the methods.

Experimental

In the alkaline method², the compound $Na_5H_2Co(IO_6)_3.xH_2O$ was prepared and its saturated aqueous solution was made approximately 2M with $HClO_4$. This was allowed to stand for several days when a dark green crystalline solid precipitated. The crystals were dissolved in minimum amount of water and reprecipitated by making the solution 2M in $HClO_4$. After 2 such precipitations, the crystals were collected and analysed.

In the acid method³, the compound, $Na_3[Co(III)-(CO_3)_3].3H_2O$, was prepared and dissolved in appropriate amount of $HClO_4$. A known amount of sodium metaperiodate was added to this solution. The green crystalline product obtained was collected from 2M $HClO_4$ as above. After 2 such precipitations the crystals were collected and analysed.

Thermal analysis: The thermograph was recorded with a Paulik-Paulik Erdey type MOM model OD-102. The derivatograph was obtained at a rate of 3°/min from room temp. to 750° using platinum crucible and samples of 150 mesh. Both

DTA and DTG were recorded with the same instrument. The peaks obtained were endothermic in nature (Fig. 1). Results are shown in Table 1.

It appears from Fig. 1 that the first step of decomposition is the elimination of water molecules. The elimination takes place via thermally unstable intermediate ($\Delta H = 3.91$ K cal/mole). A slow phase transition has been observed in the range 270-310°. The final decomposition product is Co_2O_4 .

Spectral study: Electronic spectra, both in visible and ultra violet regions, were recorded in a Hilger spectrophotometer. The results are tabulated in Table 1. The acid shows 4 bands of which 3 are in the visible to near uv region. The weak band at 22.7×10^3 cm^{-1} , which appears as a shoulder on the strong charge transfer band, is assigned to the "polynuclear band" due to a charge transfer

transition⁴ in the group $Co \begin{array}{c} \diagup O \diagdown \\ \diagdown O \diagup \end{array} Co$. The first band, which appears at 16.5×10^3 cm^{-1} , agrees well with the behaviour of several $Co(O)_6$ type complexes⁵ showing octahedral coordination round cobalt atoms. The band with high extinction coefficient in the near ultra violet region may also originate from charge transfer region. The maxima with high extinction coefficient in the ultra violet region is a charge transfer band characteristic of IO_6^{5-} species. From his studies on lithium orthoperiodate, Hauck⁶ concluded that orthoperiodates give two bands, one in the uv and the other in the near uv region. This is also in agreement with our observation.

From the energies of the visible absorption bands for the heteropoly acid, one calculates the value of the Racah parameter B to be 387 cm^{-1} (the band separation is 16B). This is very small

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 Fig. 1. Thermal decomposition of $H_3[Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}].6H_2O$.

 TABLE 1—DATA OF THERMAL DECOMPOSITION AND SPECTRA
 THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF $H_3[Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}].6H_2O$

	Obsd.	Total wt. loss		Temp. °C	
		Calcd.	TGA	DTG (Peak temp.)	
$H_3[Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}].6H_2O \rightarrow H_3Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12} + 6H_2O$	110	108	50-160	140	
$H_3Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12} \rightarrow H_3Co_4I_3O_{18}$	218	216	165-215	180	
$H_3Co_4I_3O_{18} \rightarrow Co_4I_3O_{12} + \frac{3}{2}H_2O + \frac{3}{2}[O]$	301.5	299	225-340		
$Co_4I_3O_{12} \rightarrow \frac{4}{3}Co_2O_4 + \frac{2}{3}[O] + \frac{2}{3}I_2$	808	803	350-500		
			500-750		

Spectral Data

ν in cm^{-1}	ϵ
16.5×10^3	(410)
22.7×10^3	(425)
27.4×10^3	(2454)
44.4×10^3	(4507)

compared to the values for typical cobalt(III) complexes, 510 cm^{-1} for $[Co(H_2O)_6]^{3+}$, indicating that the interaction repulsion of the 'd' electrons is much reduced, presumably by covalency⁷.

Infrared study: Infrared spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer model 621 and in Unicam SP 1000 Infrared spectrophotometer in CsI/Nujol phase and are shown in Fig. 2.

 Fig. 2. Infrared spectra of $H_3[Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}].6H_2O$.

The broad band in the range $3600-2800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to stretching O-H vibration. The broadening may be due to strong hydrogen bonding of the type O-H.....O bridge. The bridge is comparatively short as relatively broad absorption has shifted

towards lower wave number⁸. Deformation H_2O vibration has been observed at $1590-1580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with the acid. Deformation -OH vibrations bonded to iodine appear as several peaks between $1300-1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, the overtones of which appear as shoulder at 2260 cm^{-1} . The band at 935 cm^{-1} may be due to coordinated water molecules. Stretching IO-(H) vibration appears at $630-670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and that of IO vibration between 530 and 790 cm^{-1} . Deformation OIO vibrations appear as multiple peaks at $480-230 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Co-O vibrations may be present in this region. Large number of bands in this region may be due to distortion of the octahedral IO_6 group⁹⁻¹².

X-ray powder photography: X-ray powder photography has been taken with cobalt K_α radiation in a Rigaku camera at 20° . Number of lines obtained are of little importance for any proper indexing, so that parameters of the unit cell could not be carried out by this method. The results (Table 2) show that the spacings are exactly equal for the complex periodic acid obtained from the two different methods. This indicates the similarity of their crystalline nature. Crystals of the heteropolyacid, obtained by both the methods, appear identical under microscope.

TABLE 2—POWDER X-RAY RESULTS

Compound : $H_3[Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}].6H_2O$

Obtained by the acid method		Obtained by the alkaline method	
d in Å	Intensity	d in Å	Intensity
8.6266	m	8.6286	m
7.5322	s,b	7.5222	s,b
6.4751	m,b	6.4751	m,b
5.1920	w	5.1920	w
4.9455	s,b	4.9455	s,b
4.6213	w	4.6213	w
4.4257	w	4.4257	w
4.1654	w	4.1654	w
3.8624	w	3.8624	w
3.4831	w	3.4831	w
3.1699	vw,b	3.1699	vw,b
2.9164	vw,b	2.9164	vw,b
2.7684	vw	2.7684	vw
2.7008	vw	2.7008	vw
2.5153	s,b	2.5153	s,b
2.1421	s	2.1421	s
2.0656	w	2.0656	w
1.9927	m	1.9927	m
1.8800	w	1.8800	w
1.7367	w	1.7367	w
1.6711	vw	1.6711	vw
1.6004	vw	1.6004	vw
1.5657	vw	1.5657	vw
1.4544	vw	1.4544	vw
1.4268	vw	1.4268	vw
1.3756	vw	1.3756	vw

vw=very very weak, w=very weak, m=medium, s=strong, w=weak, b=broad.

Results and Discussions

Chemical and thermal analyses show that the complex polynuclear acids prepared by the above two methods are the same and have the general composition $H_3[Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}].6H_2O$, which has a formula weight of 1124. X-ray powder photography established the similarity of their crystalline nature. The compound is stable in the solid state. The aqueous solution of the compound decomposes on standing. It has been shown by potentiometric titration that the acid is tribasic with virtually identical *pk* values (*pk*~1.5) and the acid equivalent is 375.

It has been observed that though the compound $H_3[Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}].6H_2O$ is obtained from $Na_3H_2Co(IO_6)_2.xH_2O$ by acidification, the reverse reaction i.e. formation of the sodium salt cannot be accomplished by neutralising the above acid with NaOH, probably due to decomposition. It has also been observed that the sodium complex can be obtained by the alkaline method², whereas the condensed form of the complex, i.e. polynuclear acid, is obtained by the acid method³.

Nyman and Plane^{1,3} proposed two structures for the condensed compound, one chain and the other hexol like. The two have a notable difference in the number of water molecules, viz. 12 for the former and 6 for the latter. The latter structure is based on the Anderson model⁴ where one cobalt atom takes the centre of a hexagon and the three iodine and other three cobalt atoms occupy six

corners, in alternate positions, in six other hexagons. These seven octahedra are condensed by edge sharing into a flat aggregate. The compound may be formulated as $[Co\{(OH)_2Co(IO_6)\}_3]^{3-}$, should be optically active and be resolved into enantiomorphs. Although cobalt(III) compounds are inert and optical resolution of this acid was unsuccessful, some of its derivatives, e.g. L-alanine $[Co_4I_3O_{18}(OH)_4(L-ala)]^{4-}$, have been separated by Amd *et al*⁵ into optical isomers and their O.R.D., C.D. recorded. These authors also prepared some other derivatives, e.g. $[Co_4I_3O_{18}(NH_3)_6]^{3-}$ and $[Co_4I_3O_{18}(en)_3]^{3-}$, showing the complex species to contain six water molecules. Formation of 'en' complex further indicated that every two of the six water molecules take a *cis*-position to each other and this, in all probability, around each outer three cobalt atoms. All these facts suggest a hexol like structure. Our studies also reveal that the first structure of Nyman and Plane is not correct. The structure, as proposed, is not symmetric. No reason has been advanced for the different number of water molecules attached to cobalt atoms. It cannot also satisfy other experimental observations.

Electronic absorption spectra speak of the octahedral geometry round iodine and cobalt atoms. Thermal studies reveal that the twelve water molecules are linked differently to the compound in groups of six. Of these, first six molecules are lattice water, and the other six are coordinated water attached to the three outer cobalt atoms in pairs of two, that take *cis*-positions to each other. Spectral data reveal that both cobalt and iodine atoms are in octahedral environments. Racah parameter shows covalency in the solid. There is still no evidence for metal interaction in the heteropoly acid. The dark colour of the complex is due to intense electron transfer absorption in the near uv region and may also originate from distortion in the octahedral symmetry around cobalt and iodine atoms. High intensities of the electronic band may be attributed to some sort of π bonding. The intensities of the bands are high, typical of octahedral cobalt(III) complexes. Conductivity measurement¹ cannot ascertain classification of the acid to H_3A ($A=Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}$) type. But similar measurement on the sodium salt of the heteropoly acid, $Na_3[Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}].11H_2O$, has confirmed the presence of four ions (molar conductivity 330 mhos cm^2 mole⁻¹).

Considering all these facts, our suggestion is that the complex acid molecule possesses identical structure of $[Cr^{3+}(OH)_6Mo_6^{6+}O_{18}]^{3-}$ put forward by Perloff⁶ where all cobalt and iodine atoms are octahedrally arranged by edge sharing through oxygen (Fig. 3). The periodate complexes are probably H-bonded together *via* Co-O-I attachments between adjacent complexes, as has been observed in the above Cr complexes where the Cr complexes, although weakly H-bonded together *via* waters of crystallisation, are directly attached to each other only *via* two weak Cr-O-H...OMo H bonds per

Fig. 3. Probable structure of $H_3[Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}].6H_2O$.

complex since the peripheral Os lack H atoms. This will give slightly elongated exterior Co-O distances. A shorter I-O distance is also presumed. Distortion from the idealised octahedral symmetry may be there due to different I-O and Co-O bond lengths. This arrangement, however, cannot explain the presence of I-OH bond, seem to be present from infrared study. NMR studies show absence of metal hydrogen bond. The compound has been shown to be monomeric from cryoscopic study in fused $Na_2SO_4 \cdot 10H_2O^{17}$.

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